

A novel framework for analysing river planform characteristics in data-scarce regions using remote sensing data

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Abstract

The increasing demand for hydropower as a sustainable energy source in data-scarce regions, such as Central Asia, highlights the need for easy-to-apply methods for the morphological evaluation of rivers, critical to assess and maintain river health. Remote sensing data then offers a valuable approach for detecting the morphological characteristics of rivers, their development and their underlying processes. Existing studies tend to focus on either large-scale assessments, the use of single morphological metrics or the post-assessment of already implemented anthropogenic changes. This study presents a novel framework for morphological river assessment using Sentinel-2 imagery, integrating multiple metrics—channel count, river width, total wetted area, channel migration area and water occurrence frequency—to capture aspects of local braiding intensity and riverbed dynamics. We further developed suitable evaluation methods for these metrics that enable the interpretation and assessment of specific spatial and temporal aspects of morphological active river stretches. The assessment includes the seasonal and annual pattern of the morphological state, the overall bed form and dynamics and the extent of morphological uniform river sections. We applied this framework to a study site at At-Bashy River in Kyrgyzstan and established such a morphological river state. This river state includes the definition of high dynamic seasons, distinguishes six morphological sections with different channel patterns and further allows a general assessment of factors influencing channel patterns and the impact of anthropogenic pressures in braiding systems. Defining a comprehensive morphological river state using remote sensing supports more informed and sustainable hydropower development and river management strategies in data-scarce regions with the overall goal of protecting river stretches and counteracting anthropogenic alterations.

KEYWORDS

braiding, Central Asia, fluvial geomorphology, Sentinel-2, water diversions

1 | INTRODUCTION

Hydropower plays a crucial role in the context of reducing reliance on fossil fuels while meeting the increasing energy demands (Kumar et al., 2011). Central Asia, in particular, has significant potential for the development of hydropower, encompassing the implementation of both large and small hydropower plants (Azimov & Avezova, 2022). As

the demand for electricity continues to rise in these developing areas, there is also a growing trend of constructing and operating small-scale hydropower plants in these regions (Jorde et al., 2022). The various ways of hydropower implementation are, however, always linked to changes in the river's morphology (Kondolf, 1997; Kondolf et al., 2014; Winemiller et al., 2016). Therefore, achieving sustainable hydropower production requires a comprehensive description and

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assessment of river morphology, providing essential knowledge of relevant morphological processes, as well as the definition of an intended initial and final morphological river state (Buffington & Montgomery, 2013; Church, 2006; Church & Ferguson, 2015; Kondolf et al., 2016; Schumm, 1985; Surian, 2015). A critical component of such morphological assessments involves the evaluation of the potential impacts of newly constructed hydraulic structures on the associated sediment transport processes (Fantin-Cruz et al., 2020; Kondolf et al., 2014; Winemiller et al., 2016). Moreover, these assessments are essential to ensure the sustainable and efficient operation of hydropower plants in the future (Fantin-Cruz et al., 2020).

Ensuring sustainable hydropower development requires special attention to the mountainous region of Central Asia, which contains large stretches of free-flowing, pristine rivers with highly active braiding characteristics and is generally considered a biodiversity hotspot (Betz, Lauermaun, & Cyffka, 2021; CEPF, 2017; Karthe, Chalov, & Borchardt, 2015). Braided rivers are a network of multiple unstable channels formed by the frequent development and migration of bars (Surian, 2015) and are characterized by high bedload transport and high fluvial activity (Knighton, 1998; Surian, 2015). Research has demonstrated that these rivers are linked to highly variable habitat conditions and are crucial for preserving biodiversity (Belletti, Dufour, & Piégay, 2013). Given their complex morphology and significance for biodiversity, it is essential to specifically account for the formation and development of braiding in morphological assessments. Building hydropower plants or hydraulic structures on these free-flowing rivers will necessitate a comprehensive environmental assessment to ensure their protection and the preservation of their ecosystem function values.

Various metrics, such as braiding indices, have been developed to evaluate and quantify braiding activity. These metrics make use of parameters like bar lengths or areas, the number of channels and ratios of thread lengths to channel lengths (Das & Islam, 2023; Egozi & Ashmore, 2008; Friend & Sinha, 1993). They are helpful for documenting and characterizing morphological conditions, detecting morphological changes and identifying influencing factors. Additionally, these indices have recently been employed to validate numerical models (Balouchi, Rther, & Schwarzwlder, 2024; Stecca et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2016). Furthermore, Eaton, Millar, & Davidson (2010) reviewed and assessed the thresholds of parameters influencing the start of braiding and established a non-dimensional approach to differentiate single-thread rivers from anabranching rivers to braided rivers using grain size, discharge and slope. In addition to natural parameters affecting the start of braiding, human-induced alterations in rivers can impact the braiding intensity by the modification of hydrological regimes, creating lateral confinements and retaining or mining sediments (Brenna, Bizzi, & Surian, 2024; Kondolf, 1997; Vercruyse & Grabowski, 2021).

However, detailed data on river morphology and sediment transport processes, particularly at small scales, are scarce in many regions of the world. Specifically, measurements for suspended sediment, bedload, river channel form and migration rates are missing, which complicates the comprehensive assessment of river morphology. To address this data scarcity, large-scale remote sensing information about the catchment and the river itself becomes crucial (e.g. Gao et al., 2022). Remote sensing methods have generally played a

significant role in water management for three decades, evolving into important tools for environmental and water resource planning (Huang et al., 2018; Li et al., 2022; Smith, 1997). They are also often utilized to identify and assess morphological developments, see Boothroyd et al. (2021) and Pigay et al. (2020) for reviews. The availability of cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE; Gorelick et al., 2017), freely accessible data sets like Landsat and Sentinel missions and the creation of topic-specific global datasets (Allen & Pavelsky, 2018; Altenau et al., 2021; Frasson et al., 2019; Langhorst & Pavelsky, 2023; Pekel et al., 2016; Yamazaki et al., 2014) further support and facilitate the effective use of remote sensing information in water management.

Numerous studies specifically identify changes in river morphology and braiding intensity caused by human-induced alterations in the flow patterns, sediment extraction or the construction of dam structures using morphological information derived from remote sensing data (Balouchi, Rther, & Schwarzwlder, 2024; Baniya et al., 2023; Brenna, Bizzi, & Surian, 2024; Vercruyse & Grabowski, 2021; Ziliani & Surian, 2012). By analysing natural braided rivers, on the other hand, Gao et al. (2022) showed how such technologies and datasets can help to gain knowledge on characterizing and understanding the complexity of braided river functioning. Furthermore, specific tools have been developed to automatically analyse remotely obtained river features with a focus on morphological metrics (Rowland et al., 2016; Schwenk et al., 2017; Shahrood et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020). For example, SCREAM (Spatially Continuous Riverbank Erosion and Accretion Measurements, Rowland et al., 2016) analyses plan view river metrics for different river morphologies and calculates erosion and accretion rates, while RivMAP (River Morphodynamics from Analysis of Planforms, Schwenk et al., 2017) concentrates on river planform changes and the migration behaviour of meandering rivers.

Despite the availability of global datasets and innovative tools, assessing the impact of local anthropogenic activities on morphologically active braided rivers, particularly in mountainous regions like Central Asia, presents several challenges. Existing studies tend to focus on large-scale assessment in river morphology, meaning they describe long-term developments for, e.g. decades, and neglect seasonal changes in morphodynamics (Brenna, Bizzi, & Surian, 2024; Vercruyse & Grabowski, 2021; Ziliani & Surian, 2012). From a spatial perspective, they assess large study areas which encompass tens to hundreds of kilometres (Baniya et al., 2023; Brenna, Bizzi, & Surian, 2024; Vercruyse & Grabowski, 2021).

However, Bozzolan et al. (2023) emphasized the particular need for high temporal resolution data, such as Sentinel-2 images, to detect and evaluate rapid changes in river morphology, which are crucial to understanding river dynamics and their causes. These existing tools additionally concentrate on a few morphological metrics, such as the braiding intensity and migration rates (Rowland et al., 2016; Schwenk et al., 2017; Shahrood et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020), which, for one thing, are often calculated and averaged for long river stretches, neglecting local variations in the values and for another, reduce the morphological analysis to certain aspects without obtaining a holistic assessment of the morphological river state. Furthermore, current studies use remote sensing to assess anthropogenic alterations such as the construction of reservoirs or river

training (Balouchi, Rther, & Schwarzwlder, 2024; Brenna, Bizzi, & Surian, 2024; Vercruyse & Grabowski, 2021), meaning that such methods have been used to describe anthropogenic impacts afterwards, but are not used to characterize the initial morphological river states before anthropogenic alteration as part of the planning and design process.

Hence, the morphological assessment of local anthropogenic measures using remote sensing information, especially in highly active braiding rivers, is generally underrepresented in the literature. Specifically, most studies focus on (i) large-scale assessments with low spatio-temporal resolutions; (ii) the use of single or a few metrics, often neglecting the dynamic behaviour of braided rivers and without contemplating their interaction and combination; (iii) post-assessment of already implemented anthropogenic changes. In order to address these identified gaps in research, this study takes a representative case study in Central Asia, in the south-eastern part of Kyrgyzstan, with the aim of developing a novel framework to comprehensively describe the initial morphological river state, including the quantification of braiding processes in data-scarce areas. The specific objectives of this study are:

- To develop and apply a novel framework integrating innovative approaches and addressing the gaps of current morphological assessments identified above using remote sensing data

- To assess the impact of anthropogenic pressures in braiding systems, based on the application of the novel framework in the mountainous region of Kyrgyzstan.

The novelty of this framework lies in the integration of multiple morphological metrics at high spatio-temporal resolution with hydrological data. This enables a comprehensive characterization of river dynamics for pre-alteration assessments, providing a holistic description of the morphological river state through the combined use of Earth observation and hydrology.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study site

The study site is situated at the At-Bashy River in the south-eastern part of Kyrgyzstan, which is a tributary of the Naryn River in the Syr Darya catchment (Figure 1a). The region is characterized by high altitudes and minimal industrial and infrastructural development. The river displays typical mountainous features, including steep gradients and gravel riverbeds, making it a representative site of the mountainous areas in Central Asia. In this study, we specifically analyse an 11 km long river stretch located in the middle part of the east branch of the At-Bashy River (Figure 1b) influenced by an existing diversion weir (Figure 1c). The study site is at an elevation of 2,400 m above sea level (masl) and has an upstream catchment area of 1,496 km². The hydrological conditions at the site are characterized by strong intra-annual variation induced by the nivo-glacial discharge regime. Mean monthly discharge records are available from 1979 to 1996 for the former gauging station Atschikomandi, around 20 km upstream of the study site showing lower flows in the cold winter months (October to March) with a mean discharge value of 8.25 m³/s and higher flows during the warmer months (April to September) with a

mean value of 24.8 m³/s (Figure 1d). In the winter months, the study area is covered by snow and ice. In addition, suspended sediment measurements are available for this gauging station from 1969 to 1984 (Figure 1d). Similar to the flow pattern, the suspended sediment data indicate higher values in the summer months, with a mean value for June of 6 kg/s and an average annual transport value of 1.3 kg/s.

In close proximity to the diversion weir, an earth dam was constructed across the riverbed to direct the water towards the hydraulic structure, which has the purpose of diverting water for irrigation (Figure 1c). Additionally, the river runs in a concrete channel directly upstream of the weir, and artificial concrete blocks hinder the erosion of the riverbed downstream of the weir. The location of the artificial confinement of the river is shown as a red line in Figure 1c and has a lateral extent of 460 m and a longitudinal extent of 350 m. The structure comprises three weir fields with movable underflown gates and a side overfall on the right side. The diversion weir is scheduled for renovation and will be equipped with a small-scale hydropower plant (Jorde et al., 2022). The hydropower plant will include shaft hydropower plant modules to be installed directly behind two of the weir fields without altering the original design and purpose of the irrigation diversion structure. The upper part of the At-Bashy catchment consists of steep and narrow valleys with several high-gradient tributaries (Figure 1a). Downstream of the former gauging station, the valley widens with a large plain on the right side of the river. At this location, the riverbed widens, forming a multi-thread channel with several bars and islands. The diversion weir is located within this typical braided riverbed. The hydraulic structure represents the only human-made alteration in the upper and middle parts of the At-Bashy catchment, with other land uses in the catchment being low-impact and extensive. Consequently, the river upstream of the weir is in a near-natural condition from both hydrological and morphological perspectives.

2.2 | Hydrological model

A hydrological model was set up using historical daily temperature and precipitation fields from the high-resolution CHELSA v2.1 climatology (Karger et al., 2017) and ERA5 re-analysis (Hersbach et al., 2020), which were bias-corrected and spatially aggregated to elevation bands with a 500 m spacing. Hydrological simulations were carried out with the lumped rainfall-runoff model GR4J, coupled to the CemaNeige snow module as implemented in the airGR package (Perrin, Michel, & Andrassian, 2003). Glacier imbalance ablation was taken from (Rounce et al., 2023). Three warm-up years precede the simulation period to stabilize the model's internal states. Model calibration was performed on a monthly scale and employed an adaptive Latin Hypercube search to optimise multi-criteria performance metrics, followed by a split-sample validation over an independent six-year period (1991–1996). The calibration yielded satisfactory results with the following performance statistics assessed on the validation set: Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency NSE = 0.75, Root Mean Square Error RMSE = 0.383 mm/day, Percent Bias PBIAS = –5.3%. The final model outputs comprise daily discharge series from the 2017–2024 simulations and are available from Siegfried (2025). A more detailed description of the hydrological modelling is available in Supplement 1.

FIGURE 1 (a) At-Bashy catchment extents and river network obtained from HydroSHEDS (Lehner, Verdin, & Jarvis, 2008), background elevation data from a digital elevation model (Jarvis et al., 2008). (b) Orthophoto of the study area (Google earth, 18 august 2019, image © 2024 CNES / Airbus, image © 2024 Maxar technologies), dotted line indicates the extent of the subset for validation (see Supplement 5), (c) Orthophoto detail of the existing diversion weir with marked artificial channel confinement (red line) (Google earth, 18 august 2019, image © 2024 CNES/Airbus, image © 2024 Maxar technologies), (d) flow and suspended sediment data based on mean monthly values from 1970 to 1996 for flow and 1969 to 1984 for suspended sediment measured at station Atschikomandi (Hydrometeorological Service, 2022).

2.3 | Framework

We devised a novel framework involving a three-step process consisting of data preprocessing, analysis and interpretation, as shown in Figure 2. This framework was designed to specifically address the identified research gaps, as stated above, by providing a workflow from data preprocessing to result interpretation, integrating multiple metrics within a high spatio-temporal analysis of river dynamics (Objective 1). The resulting interpretation is a comprehensive description and interpretation of the analysed river stretch, enabling the assessment of anthropogenic pressures on the river dynamics (Objective 2). The following sections describe each methodological step in detail.

2.3.1 | Preprocessing

The first step of the methodological approach was the preprocessing of the Copernicus Sentinel-2 images by assessing different water detection methods from satellite images (see step ‘Preprocessing’ in Figure 2). We chose Sentinel-2 images since they are freely available globally and have a high spatial and temporal resolution of 10 m and 5 days, respectively. The images were obtained from GEE as the S2_SR_HARMONIZED product (European Union/ESA/Copernicus, 2026; Google, 2026a), a surface-reflectance, harmonized product that helps mitigate uncertainties in our data arising from atmospheric influences (Google, 2026a) and provides consistent values independent of acquisition date or sensor (European Space

FIGURE 2 Framework of this study: three-step process including data preprocessing, analysis and interpretation. The green star indicates the need for hydrological information.

Agency, 2026). The assessment of the water detection methods included the first multispectral index developed for water detection, the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI, Mc Feeters, 1996), as well as the modified version of it (Modified Normalized Difference Water Index MNDWI, Xu, 2006). In addition, we used the recently developed Multi-Spectral Water Index (MuWI, Wang et al., 2018), which not only combines the traditional (near or middle) infrared and green spectral bands but also combines several colour bands optimized using support vector machine calculations. Furthermore, we assessed two additional methods, following Zou et al. (2018) and Jones (2019), which have both been recently applied in the methodology of river width extraction (e.g. RivWidthCloud, Yang et al., 2020) and the latter additionally in the development of global water datasets (Landsat Dynamic Surface Water Extent Science Products, U.S. Geological Survey, 2022). A detailed description of these methods, including their equations and the spectral bands used, is

provided in Supplement 2. For water detection methods that contain spectral bands of different resolutions, all except NDWI, we used the default resampling method in GEE (Google, 2026b). The performance of these five methods was assessed by comparing their results with manually mapped water from a high-resolution aerial image of the study site. The steps of this performance assessment are described in Supplement 2. Using the water detection method which performed best, we then selected all available Sentinel-2 images of the study site that were free from snow, ice or clouds (see Supplement 3 for image availability), and processed them into binary images to be used as input data for the RivMAP toolbox (Schwenk et al., 2017). Due to snow and ice limitations, the image collection period was confined to April to November. The input data for the RivMAP toolbox include binary images of the study area, the date of image acquisition, the expected mean river width (set to 30 m) and the river orientation on the image (set to East–West).

2.3.2 | Analysis

The RivMAP toolbox employs binary river images to identify the river centreline and banklines, enabling the calculation of river width, curvature and migration rates for meanders (Schwenk et al., 2017). While originally developed for assessing river migration in meandering rivers, we adapted the toolbox to account for braiding characteristics, including braiding intensity.

The At-Bashy River in the study area forms side arms or threads, which have widths in the range of the spatial resolution of the Sentinel-2 images. Especially the curvature of the river in the upstream part and the intensive braiding in the downstream part pose a challenge to the identification of the centreline in the RivMAP toolbox, which is constructed as a line of subsequent water pixels. To address the issue of potential gaps between two subsequent water pixels, we applied a dilation process to expand the extent of the water pixels in the binary images within RivMAP for centreline and bankline calculations only. It is important to note that for all further calculations of metrics, we used the original binary, non-dilated image. Additionally, we calculated the river width using one method (width from mask) within RivMAP recommended for multi-thread rivers (Schwenk et al., 2017), which is not impacted by the dilated location of the banklines. The spacing for the river width calculation was chosen to be 2, corresponding to 20 m, due to the pixel resolution of 10 m.

We extended the RivMAP toolbox by extracting additional morphological metrics compared to the original version. First, we calculated the total wetted area by summing all identified water pixels since braiding rivers show significant changes in lateral extensions with varying discharge values. We also employed the lines perpendicular to the centreline identified in RivMAP to quantify the braiding intensity. This was achieved by counting the transitions from non-water pixels to water pixels along these perpendicular lines, yielding a channel count value at pixel resolution (Egozi & Ashmore, 2008). Furthermore, to assess the entire study area for braiding characteristics, we derived the mean braiding intensity as the average of all channel count values at pixel resolution.

The morphological metrics calculated by the extended RivMAP toolbox were then evaluated from a temporal and spatial perspective (see step 'Analysis' in Figure 2). To assess the temporal perspective, we utilized the averaged metrics for river width, channel count, and the total wetted area values for each image. This data was plotted as a time series to identify the annual and seasonal development of the metrics together with the simulated hydrological data. To understand the river's form and dynamics over time, we performed the spatio-temporal evaluation, where we combined all available images into one composed image representing the extent of the riverbed during the analysed period. We displayed the composed image as a water occurrence frequency map. The water occurrence frequency map represents the percentage of the period, in this case, all available images, that a pixel was detected to be covered by water and provides insights into the morphological activity of the riverbed and the spatial extent of the river. Additionally, we selected one image per year for September where the simulated discharge was closest to the mean simulated discharge for September to represent the final morphological state of the river each year. We created water difference maps based on these selected September images of two consecutive years

and calculated the area of newly formed and abandoned flow paths, useful for detecting river channel migration from one year to another. For our spatial analysis, we divided the study area into 200-m segments and calculated the distribution of all relevant metrics (water occurrence frequency, river width and channel count) for these segments using all available images. We selected a length of 200 m for this division since at least 10 times the river width is recommended for the analysis of braiding characteristics (Egozi & Ashmore, 2008), so it represents the highest resolution possible. For the river width and the channel count, this distribution includes all values at the associated resolution of all available images aggregated into the 200-m segments. For the water frequency, we used the composed water occurrence frequency map and combined the values here solely for the 200-m segments. Additionally, we employed a change point detection method based on standard deviation in Matlab (The MathWorks Inc., 2024) to detect statistical changes in space in the metrics, limiting the number of change points to a maximum of five and the minimum distance between two change points to 200 m.

Ultimately, we classified the river reach into sections with similar characteristics. We provided mean values for each metric and a mean slope value for each identified section using topographic information in the form of a digital elevation model (DEM) (Jarvis et al., 2008) along the identified centrelines. We further included a visual assessment of the stability of the channels, following Eaton, Millar, & Davidson (2010), using the water occurrence frequency, since none of the required data are available to assess the channel stability quantitatively.

2.3.3 | Interpretation

The results obtained from the described analysis provide a comprehensive description of the current morphological river state (see step 'Interpretation' in Figure 2). Such a description includes insight into the seasonal pattern, the stability of river form and its dynamics and the location of morphological changes. This step of the framework, hence, provides detailed information on the river dynamics, enabling the detection of anthropogenic pressures and the establishment of a baseline for monitoring future anthropogenic impacts.

3 | RESULTS

The following results address the two stated objectives. Sections 3.1 to 3.2 present the development and application of the novel framework (Objective 1), including the temporal, spatio-temporal and spatial evaluation of morphological metrics. Section 3.3 synthesizes these analyses to define an initial morphological river state for pre-alteration assessment and evaluates the impact of anthropogenic pressures on the braiding system (Objective 2).

3.1 | Preprocessing: water detection

From the different water detection methods, NDWI overall performed best compared to the other methods and considering different buffer sizes. The NWDI achieved the highest overall accuracies (89%) and

Kappa coefficients (61%) over all buffer sizes and reached high User and Producer Accuracy values, followed by the MuWI, MNDWI and then the methods after Zou and Jones (Supplement 2). No significant differences in performance were observed when changing the buffer sizes in combination with the NDWI. Hence, we selected a buffer size of one pixel since Rossi et al. (2023) showed higher accuracies for smaller buffer sizes.

3.2 | Analysis

3.2.1 | Temporal evaluation

The temporal development of the morphological metrics wetted area, river width and channel count is shown in Figure 3. We overlaid the metrics with the simulation results of the hydrological models for the available period (2017 to 2024), which allows a

temporal comparison of morphology and hydrology. The three morphological metrics show similar seasonal behaviour with higher values in late spring and summer and lower values in autumn and winter, starting from September. The flow data follows the same seasonal pattern, with mostly one or two main flood peaks in the middle of April and the beginning of May, with a duration of around two days.

We thus recognize a low-dynamic and a high-dynamic season from April until August and September until November, respectively (see Supplement 3 for the image availability for these periods). Figure 3 also shows the boxplots of the three metrics and the simulated discharge divided into these seasons. During the high-dynamic season, a mean wetted area of 530.000 m² and a mean river width of 37.1 m occurs, and on average, 1.6 channels are formed and a mean discharge of 20.2 m³/s was simulated whereas, for the low-dynamic season, a wetted area of 260.000 m², a mean river width of 19.1 m, and on average 1.2 channels and 10.2 m³/s are identified. The

FIGURE 3 Left: temporal development of morphological metrics at at-Bashy River for 2017 to 2024 (from top to bottom: wetted area in m², river width in m, channel count [-], simulated discharge in m³/s). The metrics are displayed as data points representing one image each. Right: boxplots for all parameters divided into high- and low-dynamic seasons (April to august and September to November, respectively), boxes indicate 25th to 75th percentiles, central mark indicates the median, whiskers most extreme data points, '+' marker outliers.

boxplots generally show a high variability in the values for the high-dynamic season, whereas the values are much more constant in the low-dynamic season. This difference in variability confirms the division into these two dynamic periods.

All morphological metrics show the highest values for 14 June 2022. However, the flood peak occurred earlier, at the beginning of May, which coincides only with the second-highest values. Due to low image availability in April and May, we see that not many pictures actually capture the high peak flows. This means that the variability seen in the metrics is a result of the variable flows during summer instead of the high peak discharge due to snowmelt.

3.2.2 | Spatio-temporal evaluation

Figure 4a displays the water occurrence frequency obtained by combining all 120 images. Red pixels represent pixels with higher water occurrence frequency, meaning that in a high number of images, these pixels were defined to be water. Blue pixels, on the other hand, indicate low water occurrence frequencies, meaning areas defined to be water for fewer images. The map thus detects regions of high and low riverbed dynamics. Highly dynamic sections can be found in the middle and lower part of the study site, up to 3 km upstream of the weir and starting again 1 km downstream of the weir. The upper part of

FIGURE 4 Spatio-temporal development of morphodynamics at at-Bashy River. (a): water occurrence frequency map composed for 2017 to 2024, (b): water difference maps, (c): migration area in m^2 for the corresponding water differences maps for 2018 to 2019 until 2023 to 2024.

the study site and the area directly downstream of the weir are characterized by stable river channels with higher water occurrence frequencies.

Figure 4b shows the water difference maps for the years starting from comparing 2018 and 2019 (see Supplement 4 for exact dates and discharges for the selected images). Since we only obtained four images for 2017 and no image for September, we neglected this year in the analysis. Black pixels represent areas that were detected to be water in the previous year but not recognized to be covered by water in the following year. In contrast, green pixels are newly formed channels or regions newly covered by water. Similar to the water occurrence frequency map (Figure 4a), these maps show the difference in river channel migration behaviour and channel stability over the study area. Since less area in the upper parts is black or green, lower migration can be detected for this river part. Similarly, the river channel directly downstream of the weir is stable, whereas the river in the middle and lower parts shows river channel migration from year to year. However, comparing 2018 with 2019, a general shift in the water course can be seen in the upper part, where a new path is now located more to the south. In the more active middle part, the formation of a single new flow path is visible when comparing 2020 and 2021. This flow path moved even more to the north in the following year. Overall, the highest channel migration area within the entire study area is detected for comparing 2023 and 2024, where, due to the construction of the hydropower plant, from September onwards,

the river was diverted towards the south. This new artificially created flow path is therefore the reason for the high migration values between these years (Figure 4c).

We can generally detect different channel-forming processes over the study area with low channel migration in the upper part of the river, where one main river channel existed over the analysed timespan, and only sidearms are regularly changing their appearance. In contrast, in the middle of the study area, singular threads are formed or dried up from one year to another, but one main river channel remains, which can also be seen from the water occurrence frequency shown in Figure 4a. In the lower part of the study area, no main stable flow path is visible over the years in the water occurrence frequency map (Figure 4a) and regular changes in river threads are detected by the high amount of black and green pixels in the water difference maps (Figure 4b).

3.2.3 | Spatial evaluation

Figure 5 shows the spatial distribution of the metrics water occurrence frequency, river width and channel count as boxplots. The figure displays the study area with the flow direction from right to left, where 0 km represents the most upstream point of the study area. All values are related to the centreline of the associated image, which means the river stretch length (x-axis) then equals the centreline

FIGURE 5 Spatial development of morphological metrics (from top to down): water occurrence frequency in %, channel count [-] and river width [m], aggregated for 200-m segments looking downstream with the flow direction from right to left, where 0 km at the river stretch represents the most upstream point of the study area. The grey boxes indicate the region, which is anthropogenically altered by the weir and the earth dam.

length. The vertical black lines indicated the location of the detected change points. Since the centreline length varies from image to image due to the shifting watercourses, we cannot fix the weir to a specific location but rather need to indicate the region where the earth dam, the weir and the stabilized riverbed are found to kilometre 6 to 7 (grey box in Figure 5).

All metrics change their mean values and their variance over the study site. The water occurrence frequency values show generally quite high variability, but also a spatial trend is visible with higher values at the beginning of the study site, as well as at kilometres 6 to 7.5. These higher values indicate a stable riverbed. The middle part of the study site and the most downstream part show lower values and lower variances for the water occurrence frequency, meaning that the riverbed changes actively here. The change points for the water occurrence frequency were detected to be at 1, 3.5, 6.3, 7.9 and 9.2 km.

The channel count metric shows the reversed trend as the water occurrence frequency, with higher median values and more variability in the middle and the lower part of the river stretch. The change points detected for the channel count are 3, 5.3, 6.8, 7.2 and 8.9 km.

The river width shows generally high variabilities with several outliers, but lower variabilities are documented for the most upstream part of the river and the region of kilometre 6.4 to 7.1. No clear trend can be detected for the median values of the river width. The change points for the metric river width are located at kilometre 4.2, 6.2, 6.8 and 7.7.

In general, water occurrence frequency shows the clearest spatial pattern. We can use this spatial pattern to identify regions with higher morphological activity and frequent river migration (kilometre 3 to 6 and 7.5 to 10.4), which also coincide with the formation of river threads and sidearms, which link back to the metric of channel count. Most importantly, we see that all metrics change in the anthropogenically altered section of the earth dam and the weir structure (kilometre 6 to 7), where for all metrics change points were detected. This is especially interesting in contrast to the rest of the river stretch, where no spatial linkage between the detected change points of the three metrics can be seen.

3.3 | Interpretation: Morphological River state at at-Bashy River

The spatial and temporal evaluation provides a comprehensive description of the current morphological state of the At-Bashy River. Regarding temporal trends, we observed a seasonal pattern in the morphological activity, with high- and low-dynamic seasons. These high-dynamic seasons are characterized by generally higher and more variable values for the morphological metrics and are linked to the higher and more variable flow values observed during that time (Boxplots in Figure 3). Based on this high variance in the morphological metrics during that time, we can assume that morphological changes primarily occur during these seasons and are linked to individual high-flow events.

The extent of dynamic adjustment in river form, however, varies across the study area. We, therefore, divided the study area into sections with similar morphological characteristics using the results of the water difference maps and the water occurrence frequency map (Figure 4), together with the spatial development of the morphological metrics (Figure 5). By using the change points of water occurrence frequency, which visually shows the clearest spatial pattern, we identified six distinct sections—three upstream and three downstream of the weir (Figure 6). Section 1 is characterized by one main stable channel, which remained the same over the analysed years, and has regularly flooded sidearms but low migration to the sides, making it a stable anabranching river stretch. In Section 2, the riverbed is wider, and from the water difference maps and the water occurrence frequency, it is evident that new threads are regularly formed, indicating an unstable riverbed. This section also exhibits a higher braiding intensity of 1.49 and a lower water occurrence frequency of 23.7% than the previous one, 1.21 and 36.8% respectively, classifying it as a braiding river stretch. Section 3 has an even higher number of threads per cross-section (1.74) and a lower water occurrence frequency, indicating a braiding river stretch as well. Section 4 is notably influenced by human alteration, spanning from approximately 200 m upstream of the weir to 850 m downstream of the weir. High values for the water occurrence frequency (21.2%) and the low mean value for channel

FIGURE 6 Identified morphological river sections with similar morphological behaviour and their corresponding mean metric values. For the visualization of the river sections, the water occurrence frequency map is used (compare Figure 4). The classification follows Eaton, Millar, & Davidson (2010).

count (1.25) lead to the classification of a stable single-thread channel. Section 5 demarcates the start of the natural morphological dynamics again. The presence of multiple channels (1.46) and frequent river migration (17.1%) classifies this section as a braiding stretch. Finally, Section 6 shows the most intense braiding process of the study area, evidenced by a combination of a high channel count value (1.71), the widest river width (32 m) and the lowest water occurrence frequency (13.8%).

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Framework development

In this study, we developed and applied a novel framework for the comprehensive assessment of a morphological river state using remote sensing. To address the identified gaps in current literature, our approach (i) calculates morphological metrics at the highest possible spatial and temporal resolution, enabling detection of local and seasonal variations; (ii) integrates multiple complementary metrics to capture different aspects of braiding intensity and riverbed dynamics; and (iii) establishes an initial morphological river state for planning purposes rather than post-alteration assessment.

Specifically, we calculated the morphological metrics at the highest possible resolution, meaning spatially the resolution of the dataset (Sentinel-2, 10 m) or temporally for all images available without cloud or snow and ice cover. This was possible by making use of the RivMAP toolbox (Schwenk et al., 2017), for which the effectiveness of analysing morphological metrics and their development over time has already been demonstrated, and which calculates most metrics in a pixel resolution or a user-selected spacing. This resolution is necessary to identify spatial differences in the analysed river section itself, which is lost when averaging over longer sections. Similarly, by analysing each image separately in the temporal analysis, we gain information on intra-annual changes in the morphology, which is essential when identifying dynamic periods during the year or, in general, capturing the variability of morphology. The need for these high temporal resolution data was also recognized by Bozzolan et al. (2023), who highlighted this aspect as the basis to evaluate rapid changes crucial to understanding river dynamics and their causes.

The integration of multiple metrics was achieved by using traditional metrics such as the river width, the water-covered area and the channel count averaged for the study site. Additionally, we used the channel count value at pixel resolution, calculated the water occurrence frequency and expressed annual changes in the form of water difference maps. This combination of different metrics and the different ways of evaluating them allows the description of several aspects, such as river extent and width, but also the river's dynamics spatially and temporally. One example here is that by only looking at the river width and the channel count in the third and sixth sections (Figure 6), no difference in the braiding process could be observed, but the inclusion and visual representation of the water occurrence frequency and the water difference maps make it possible to identify a much higher dynamics in Section 6 in comparison to Section 3.

This combination of a variety of metrics calculated from high-resolution data finally allows the establishment of an assessment of a comprehensive morphological river state. This step is especially crucial

in defining an initial morphological river state, important during planning processes and facilitating monitoring in data-scarce regions (Buffington & Montgomery, 2013; Church, 2006; Church & Ferguson, 2015; Kondolf et al., 2016; Schumm, 1985; Surian, 2015). The outputs of this novel framework for our study site are the seasonal and annual morphological patterns and the definition of morphological active periods, the detection of frequently changing river channels and spatial development of the overall riverbed form and dynamics, as well as the identification of years of high morphological dynamics. The developed novel methodology of this study therefore fulfilled the intended purpose of analysing essential aspects of highly dynamic rivers, providing a comprehensive morphological characterization and the definition of the current morphological river state.

Nevertheless, we acknowledge uncertainties arising within our framework, mostly linked to the availability and accuracy of the dataset analysed. Specifically, sources of uncertainty include the limited temporal and spatial availability of Sentinel-2 imagery, the performance of the water detection methods, the hydrological model and the resulting simulated discharge values. We focus our discussion on the spatial and temporal resolution of Sentinel-2 imagery and its impact on water detection, as we consider this the primary source of uncertainty in assessing the morphological river state. This aspect is particularly relevant because it does not change when applying the framework to other study sites, since the spatial and temporal resolution of Sentinel-2 data is globally consistent and thus represents a systematic constraint of the framework rather than a site-specific limitation.

We chose Sentinel-2 images for this study as they are freely available globally and have a high spatial and temporal resolution compared to, for instance, Landsat datasets. The temporal resolution of Sentinel-2 also provides the possibility to closely evaluate river dynamics and to identify and assess morphological changes in time, as recommended by Ziliani & Surian (2012), Piégay et al. (2020) and Bozzolan et al. (2023). For this particular study site, the combination of snow cover and frequent cloud cover results in a limited number of usable images in spring (April and May). This constrains the accurate documentation of spring discharge conditions, particularly individual high-flow events, and therefore prevents a quantitative assessment of associated morphological changes. The spatial resolution of 10 m might be limited in recognizing narrow river channels in braiding rivers, especially affecting the calculation of the river width and the channel count. This limitation is associated with the 'spatial accuracy' defined by Grabowski et al. (2014) and is the reason why several studies tend towards higher-resolution datasets obtained from UAVs or airplanes instead of satellites for morphological evaluations (e.g. Carbonneau et al., 2012; Rivas Casado et al., 2016). The influence of the spatial resolution is expected to be higher when using other water detection methods such as indices, e.g. MNDWI and MuWI, which include spectral bands with a resolution of 20 m, compared to the NDWI used within this study, which includes only spectral bands of 10 m resolution. Using other resampling methods, as done in Kirby et al. (2024), could reduce this effect and are worth testing if indices other than NDWI are used.

To test the accuracy and usability of the Sentinel-2 dataset for this framework, we included a subset validation in this study (Supplement 5). We compared the results of the extended RivMAP tool for a Sentinel-2 image and a high-resolution aerial image obtained

by a UAV on the same day for a subset of our study site (Figure 1b). We calculated river width and channel count for both images in the same way and also detected change points in these metrics. Figure 7 shows both binary images, where white pixels represent water-covered areas. The red pixels indicated the centreline identified by the RivMAP tool, perpendicular to which the morphological metrics are calculated. The graphs below the images show the spatial development of the morphological metrics, river width and channel count, for each image, where the centreline length starts from zero in the most upstream part. Black lines indicate again the detected change points.

As expected, we could see an underestimation in the explicit values for river width and channel count, which can be explained by the fact that small sidearms are not detected for the Sentinel-2 images. However, interestingly, a similar spatial pattern of the morphological metrics was observed, which is shown by the similar locations of the detected change points and which fully supports the idea and objective of our study to use remote sensing information to detect a spatial development in the river's morphology.

Since we did not aim for the explicit calculation of morphological metrics or the identification of the morphology at a particular flow condition, but for a comprehensive description of the river's morphology temporally and spatially, the subset validation proves the validity and usability of this novel framework. Therefore, we showed that the framework is sufficient to capture the spatial variation in morphology at a study site in data-scarce regions.

In addition, the hydrological model also contains uncertainties as it is calibrated using monthly mean values for the period 1979–1996 (Supplement 1). This relatively coarse temporal resolution of the calibration data may affect the accuracy of the simulated daily discharge

values. In particular, we expect greater uncertainty in peak discharge estimates, as short-term high-flow events are smoothed out by monthly averaging in the calibration data, preventing a direct comparison of these events. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the simulated discharge values is sufficient to identify a discharge dependence of the morphological metrics and to distinguish between low-dynamic and high-dynamic seasons (Section 3.2.1).

4.2 | From interpretation to channel pattern understanding

The framework described in this study also allowed us to address our second objective of a closer understanding of natural morphodynamics and the effects of anthropogenic pressures on braiding systems. We performed this study at the At-Bashy River in Kyrgyzstan, which is still in a near-natural condition and is characterized by explicit features common in this region (Betz, Lauermaun, & Cyffka, 2021). As expected, we see the known discharge dependence that the morphological metrics are generally sensitive to the flow conditions (Egozi & Ashmore, 2008; Bozzolan et al., 2023). Higher values occur at times of higher discharges, with a doubling in mean discharge leading to almost doubling of the mean wetted area and the mean river width, as well as increasing the mean channel count by a third. Interestingly, we observed that even small changes in the discharge lead to a variation in the metrics, indicating that the river morphology actively reacts to the flow variability during the summer period. This means that not only the first discharge peak due to snow melt, but probably also other discharge peaks alter the riverbed, making it

FIGURE 7 Binary image obtained from Sentinel-2 and UAV data for the 7th of August in 2024 for the extent of the subset. And display of the spatial development of the morphological metrics river width and channel count obtained by the RivMAP tool for each binary image. Hint: white pixels represent pixels covered by water and black pixels dry areas. Red pixels show the location of the identified centreline.

generally highly dynamic during the summer period with channel count values above 2 and river width values above 50 m.

Ultimately, we observed different channel patterns in the study area (Figure 6). Assuming that only Section 4 is anthropogenically altered due to the local effect of the backwater at the weir and the spatially limited artificial confinement (longitudinal extent of 350 m, Figure 1c), we can gain knowledge on the natural processes affecting the channel patterns in the study area. Braiding typically occurs in rivers with high sediment supply, erodible banks and high stream powers (Knighton, 1998), which leads to the assumption that these conditions are generally fulfilled for the study site. Eaton, Millar, & Davidson (2010) used the dimensionless discharge, which combines the bankfull discharge and the median grain size of the substrate, and the valley slope to differentiate between single-thread, anabranching and braiding rivers, where braiding occurs at higher slopes. The calculated thresholds further account for the presence or absence of vegetation, which is generally recognized as a significant factor (e.g. Gran & Paola, 2001; Tal & Paola, 2010; Church & Ferguson, 2015). Interestingly, since we do not expect a drastic change in discharge within the study area and observe slopes in a similar range, the decisive factors here are probably the grain size and riverbed and bank stability, possibly influenced by vegetation. From the orthophoto in Figure 1b, we observe more vegetation patches in the upstream part and less lateral erosion, which supports this hypothesis.

Regarding the human influence of braiding formation, we see that the weir with the channelization and change in slope has a strong influence on all metrics and changes them quite abruptly, since change points are detected for all metrics in this region. The diversion weir directly affects approximately one kilometre of the river morphology due to changes in slope and lateral confinement (Section 4, Figure 6). Within this influenced area, the river forms a single-thread and stable riverbed, which had the same extent and location in all analysed years, in contrast to the other sections. It requires an additional 1.5 km for the natural slope and braiding characteristics to reappear (Section 5, Figure 6). Even though this anthropogenic impact is visible, its effects are localized (around one kilometre) and do not persist downstream, allowing the river to resume its natural morphological dynamics. The current hydraulic structure has several effects on the river, including a reduced discharge, a decreased slope upstream and downstream, an artificial drop at the structure itself, lateral confinement due to earth dams guiding the water, the flow regulation gates and corresponding impoundment upstream of the weir. Considering that the reduction in discharge is generally minimal and only occurs during the summer months and that the gates are fully opened during high-flow periods, we assume that neither the reduction in discharge nor the impoundment, potentially trapping sediments, is responsible for the observed changes in morphology.

We argue that the alteration of slope and the lateral confinement are the decisive factors influencing the morphological pattern at the weir. Erodible banks and high stream power gradually re-establish around 800 m downstream, where the bank protection and altered slope terminate, renewing the complex channel formation and perpetuating it towards the end of the study area. Additionally, we assume that the weir maintains sediment connectivity, especially when the gates are fully opened for several months annually and prevents long-term sediment trapping. Observing braiding characteristics downstream of the weir implies a sufficiently high sediment supply, suggesting that sediments

can traverse the weir structure, or that the wide riverbed and the erodible banks can mitigate the reduction in sediment supply due to the weir. For the planned implementation of the hydropower plant, we expect no further deterioration of the morphology as the alteration of slope and the lateral confinement remain the same. The chosen hydropower plant type will also ensure sediment connectivity (Jorde et al., 2022).

4.3 | Future applications of the novel framework

Our study is relevant in the context of sustainable river management and provides the baseline for a potentially more sustainable hydropower development. As mentioned by several authors, a systematic description and evaluation of river morphology is a key element in sustainable river management, as it provides an initial river state or a target state (Buffington & Montgomery, 2013; Church, 2006; Kondolf et al., 2016; Surian, 2015). Obtaining such a comprehensive description of a morphological river state using freely accessible remote sensing datasets, as done in this study, finally allows us to extend such an assessment to rivers in data-scarce regions, which are often still in near-natural conditions and where maintaining their natural river state is of high importance. Especially in the context of increasing anthropogenic alterations and increasing use of water resources across different sectors, sustainable river management is crucial to limit or even prevent the negative effects on these multi-stressed rivers.

Our framework, as described here, is transferable to other rivers and other management questions. Criteria for transfer include the river type, the study site location and the availability and quality of input data. We recommend applying the framework to rivers with high morphological activity and dynamic riverbed changes, widths exceeding the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2, and located in remote regions where in situ data collection is difficult or prohibitively time- and cost-intensive and therefore higher-resolution data, such as river cross-sections, UAV or LiDAR or comparable surveys, are unavailable. The availability of hydrological data proved very useful for a holistic assessment at our study site and is therefore expected to be of great value at other study sites as well. The application of this framework, hence, requires prior knowledge of the dominant morphological processes and basic information on river width and periods of potential cloud or snow cover.

At the same time, our framework is flexible and can easily be adapted to address other research questions to integrate or omit some morphological metrics, or to build upon other datasets. As shown by the subset validation, such other datasets can be high-resolution UAV data or even plan-view outputs of numerical models. The framework may also serve to estimate the extent of flood and to identify potential zones at risk, as well as to further guide more detailed assessments and possible in situ data-collection campaigns by identifying zones of interest. The generally applicable framework should nevertheless follow the same overall workflow: preprocessing the underlying dataset, spatial and temporal analysis of the river morphology and finally a detailed interpretation, leading to a comprehensive assessment of the morphological river state.

Further studies building upon this framework at our study site could then include a specific analysis of the individual high-flow events and their effects on morphology and a quantification of sediment transport rates. Moreover, the numerical simulation of

hydrodynamic and morphodynamic processes would provide insights into sediment transport processes for current and future conditions, enabling the critical assessment of anthropogenic alterations.

5 | CONCLUSION

In this study, we developed and applied a novel framework for a comprehensive morphological river assessment using remote sensing, integrating multiple morphological metrics and analytical steps. In contrast to existing morphological studies encompassing large-scale applications, relying on a limited number of morphological metrics and focusing on post-alteration assessments, our methodology enables an assessment of local morphology, analyses a combination of several morphological metrics spatially and temporally and leads to a holistic description of the morphological river state for the planning and monitoring phase. Such a framework is crucial for data-scarce regions that mostly rely on such large-scale imagery. For the study site, At-Bashy River in Kyrgyzstan, we revealed distinct seasonal morphodynamics, identified spatial variability in channel patterns, and defined the river sections influenced by an existing diversion weir. Defining the current morphological state of rivers using remote sensing is critical for designing sustainable hydropower solutions, especially in data-scarce regions with still highly dynamic and pristine rivers. Such approaches hence facilitate sustainable river management aiming at minimizing anthropogenic alterations on river morphology. The framework provides the first step of morphological assessments and guides future work that should incorporate more quantitative assessment of the link between hydrology and sediment transport and include higher-resolution imagery, field surveys and numerical simulations.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Hannah Schwedhelm: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing – initial draft. **Tobias Siegfried:** conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – reviewing and editing, funding acquisition. **Roser Casas-Mulet:** conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – reviewing and editing. **Antonia Dallmeier:** conceptualization, methodology, writing – reviewing and editing. **Nils Rther:** conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – reviewing and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Hannah Schwedhelm, upon request.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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